

Abstract

CYTOTOXIC ACTIVITY OF *Euphorbia pulcherrima* (POINSETTIA) ETHANOLIC LEAF EXTRACT ON A549 HUMAN LUNG ADENOCARCINOMA CELL LINE

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Euphorbia pulcherrima (poinsettia) is generally characterized by their bright red and green foliage. It is widely cultivated plant known for its ornamental and medicinal uses. This study aimed to determine the cytotoxic activity of *E. pulcherrima* ethanolic leaf extract against A549 human lung adenocarcinoma cell line. The leaves were extracted in 300 ml of ethanol using Soxhlet apparatus and the product was concentrated using a rotary evaporator. MTT assay was used to determine the cytotoxic activity of *E. pulcherrima*. Eight two-fold dilutions of the sample were used as treatments starting from 100 µg/ml down to 0.78125 µg/ml. Doxorubicin served as positive control while dimethyl Sulphoxide (DMSO) served as negative control. The results indicated that the cells treated with highest concentration (100 µg/ml) of *E. pulcherrima* extract is most effective in the said concentration. There was a noticeable decrease in the population of the cells compared to the photographs taken with treatments of lower concentration.

Keywords: *Euphorbia pulcherrima*, Cytotoxicity, Doxorubicin, DMSO, MTT Assay

Introduction

In the Philippines, lung cancer is the leading cause of cancer-related deaths among men and is the third cause of cancer deaths among women, ranked after breast and cervical cancer according to the 2012 Globocan statistics of the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). The agency also concluded that an estimate of 10 Filipinos die of smoking-related diseases every hour, and that 90 percent of lung cancers are linked to cigarette smoking, making smoking the leading cause of lung cancer. Close to 10,000 Filipinos die every year because of lung cancer according to the data published in 2016 by the World Health Organization (WHO). In 2017, cases of lung cancer deaths in the Philippines reached 11,365 or 1.84 percent of total deaths according to the data published by WHO. Lung cancer can be potentially acquired by any individual. However, family history, lifestyle choices, and environmental exposures are factors that increase the risk of certain groups of people to lung cancer.

There are two main types of lung cancer, small cell lung cancer and non-small cell lung cancer. These categories refer to the morphology of the cancer cells microscopically. Non-small cell lung cancer is more common than small cell lung cancer. The type along with the stage of lung cancer determines what kind of treatment will be needed. According to Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), these two types of cancer may be treated in several ways. People suffering from non-small cell lung cancer may be treated with surgery, where a doctor removes the cancer tissue or with chemotherapy, which employs the use

of medication in the form of pills or intravenous fluid to shrink or kill the tumor. Radiation therapy may also be used, which uses high-energy rays much like X-rays to kill the cancer, or targeted therapy, which uses drugs to block the growth and spread of the cancer cells. People with small cell lung cancer are usually treated with radiation therapy and chemotherapy.

Radiation therapy and chemotherapy have been known to cause harmful effects to the human body according to University of Pittsburgh Medical Center (UPMC) in 2016. Chemotherapy is a systemic treatment, which means the drugs administered to prevent the spread of the disease works its way through the whole body. Consequently, it damages even healthy cells, depending on the type and amount of chemotherapy drug used and how the body reacts to it. Most cancer patients have already weakened immune system, thus magnifying the adverse effects of chemotherapy drugs. According to UPMC, some of the side effects of chemotherapy include: anemia, risk of infection, and bruising due to the damage to blood-forming cells in the bone marrow; temporary hair loss due to the damage to hair follicles; and nausea, loss of appetite, constipation or diarrhea due to the damage afflicted to the cells in the mouth, digestive tract and reproductive tract. More severe adverse effects of chemotherapy drugs include conditions resulting from damage to the cells in the heart, kidney, bladder, lungs, and nervous system. On the other hand, radiation therapy is another form of treatment where high-energy particles or waves are used to kill cancer cells by damaging their DNA. Unlike chemotherapy which is systemic,

radiation therapy is a localized treatment – it only affects the tumor or the site where the radiation is delivered. Similar to chemotherapy, it also damages healthy cells in the body. According to UPMC, radiation therapy may be prescribed on its own, however it is frequently combined with chemotherapy as a comprehensive cancer treatment program. This practice amplifies the adverse effects of both treatments, often damaging major body organs and systems. The complications regarding chemotherapy and radiation therapy have led researchers to seek for alternative medicine in the management of lung cancer.

Natural methods have been used since the ancient times to treat illnesses. Plants have been utilized for their health and medical benefits for several thousand years. Today, plants are being used to treat several health concerns and conditions, including allergies, wounds, burns, headaches, gastrointestinal issues, among others. It is also widely used as management for cancer patients. According to Cancer Research UK in 2015, herbal medicine is one of the most commonly used alternative therapies by people with cancer. Patients prefer plant-based medicine in the premise that it does not give harmful side effects to the body, unlike synthetic drugs that are manufactured with a lot of chemicals in them. Some of the plants used for the management of lung cancer include *Platycodon grandiflorus*, *Morus alba* (white mulberry), *Prunus armeniaca* (Armenian plum), *Rhus verniciflua* (Chinese lacquer tree), *Perilla frutescens* (beefsteak plant), *Stemona japonica*, *Tussilago farfara* (coltsfoot), and *Draba nemorosa* (woodland draba) (Yin, Wei, Jian, & Yang, 2013).

It is in this context that this study has been conceptualized to determine the anti-lung cancer property of poinsettia. The poinsettia, *Euphorbia pulcherrima*, is an ornamental plant of particular seasonal interest. It is recognized as the most economically important potted plant worldwide (Ecke III, Faust, Higgins, & Williams, 2004). It is popularly known as Christmas flower because of how it is widely used in Christmas displays. History of the plant dates back to 14th century, cultivated by the Aztecs who initially called it Cuetlaxochitl. Poinsettias are indigenous to Mexico, but are widely cultivated across the globe because of its popularity as Christmas ornament. The name poinsettia recognizes Joel Roberts Poinsett, a botanist and the first United States Minister to Mexico, who introduced the plant in the United States in 1828 (Fry, 1994). Alternative names for the poinsettia are nochebuena, star of Bethlehem, and Christmas star.

Euphorbia pulcherrima is a shrub or small tree that belongs to the family *Euphorbiaceae* and is generally characterized by their bright red and green foliage. The plant has dentate, dark green leaves that measure 3 inches to 6 inches in length (Rahman & Akter, 2013). The red bracts, or modified leaves, are often mistaken as flowers. The actual flowers are quite small, located at the center of the leaf bunch as yellow structures and are called cyathia. The distinct colored bracts vary in different species and may be orange, pale green, cream, pink, white or marbled (Rahman & Akter, 2013). The plant typically reaches a height of about 1 foot to 13 feet (Rahman & Akter, 2013). Poinsettias are found in the

wild in deciduous tropical forests. The large, dark green, oval leaves have “toothed” sides and pointed tips. The color of the bracts is a product of photoperiodism, where the plant requires twelve hours of darkness for at least five days in a row to change color (Rahman & Akter, 2013).

Poinsettia’s family, *Euphorbiaceae*, or the spurge family, is a family of flowering plants with over 300 genera and around 7,500 species (Rahman & Akter, 2013). In a study conducted by Rahman and Akter in 2013, different species of the family *Euphorbiaceae* have been identified to have medicinal uses. *Euphorbia hirta* plant is astringent and hemostatic, chiefly used for cough and bowel complaints, and its juice is known to be effective against dysentery, diarrhea, and amoebiasis (Rahman & Akter, 2013). The juice of the stem of *Euphorbia tirucalli* is known to be useful in asthma, whooping cough, leprosy, gonorrhea, and dyspepsia (Rahman & Akter, 2013). Its latex can be applied to warts and in cases of toothache and rheumatism and the root is used as vesicant (Rahman & Akter, 2013). The seeds of *Euphorbia helioscopia* are administered with roasted pepper for the treatment of cholera (Rahman & Akter, 2013). The fresh plant of *Euphorbia thymifolia* is considered vulnerary and galactagogue, and is used for various eye infections, sores, atrophy, and breast pain (Rahman & Akter, 2013). The juice of its plant is used for diarrhea and dysentery, and also parasites like ringworm (Rahman & Akter, 2013). These studies led to the interest of the researchers to know more about *Euphorbia pulcherrima*’s medicinal property, specifically its ability to kill cancer cells.

Research Locale

The research study was conducted at the Mammalian Cell Culture Laboratory of the Institute of Biology of the University of the Philippines Diliman, Quezon City. The facility contains all the necessary materials, equipment, reagents, and other apparatus needed in the conduct of the research study. The Mammalian Cell Culture Laboratory also provided the A549 human lung adenocarcinoma cell line and provides optimal condition for the storage and processing of the cell line.

Materials and Methods

A. Plant Collection

Aerial parts of *Euphorbia pulcherrima* were obtained from Silang, Cavite. The sample was brought to and authenticated by the Bureau of Plant Industry in Manila City, Metro Manila. The sample was stored in a cool, dry place under shade until utilization.

B. Preparation of Extract

100 grams of *Euphorbia pulcherrima* leaves was weighed using an analytical balance. The leaves were washed using distilled water and were air-dried under shade for 24 hours. After drying, the leaves were subjected to a laboratory blender until smaller leaf portions were obtained. From this, the researchers obtained 15 grams of fine leaf portions. The leaves were extracted in 300 ml of ethanol using a Soxhlet apparatus. The product was concentrated in vacuo at 40

degrees Celsius using a rotary evaporator. The extract obtained was stored in an airtight container at 4 degrees Celsius until utilization.

C. MTT Assay

The MTT Cytotoxicity Assay performed in this study was adapted from Mosmann (1983). In detail, cells were seeded at 4×10^4 cells/mL in sterile 96-well microtiter plates. The plates were incubated overnight at 37 degrees Celsius and 5% CO₂. Eight two-fold dilutions of the sample were used as treatments starting from 100 µg/mL down to 0.78125 µg/mL. Doxorubicin served as positive control while dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) served as negative control. Following incubation, cells were treated with each extract dilution. The treated cells were again incubated for 72 hours at 37 degrees Celsius and 5% CO₂. After incubation, the media was removed and 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) dye at 5 mg/mL phosphate buffered solution was added. The cells were again incubated at 37 degrees Celsius and 5% CO₂ for 4 hours. After which, DMSO was used to dissolve the formazan crystals formed by the reduction of the dye by the live cells. Absorbance was read at 570 nanometers.

Results and Discussion

Cytotoxic Activity Measurement by Spectrophotometric Method

Table 1. Absorbance readings of treated A549 cells.

Trial 1											
Treatment											
DMSO				Doxorubicin				<i>Euphorbia pulcherrima</i>			
Conc. (µg/mL)	Absorbance			Conc. (µg/mL)	Absorbance			Conc. (µg/mL)	Absorbance		
			Ave.				Ave.				Ave.
10.000	0.52	0.462	0.491	10.000	0.335	0.341	0.338	100	0.637	0.348	0.493
3.333	0.506	0.489	0.498	3.333	0.19	0.153	0.172	50	0.437	0.447	0.442
1.111	0.506	0.516	0.511	1.111	0.26	0.298	0.279	25	0.431	0.461	0.446
0.370	0.514	0.495	0.505	0.370	0.455	0.414	0.435	12.5	0.439	0.46	0.450
0.123	0.523	0.508	0.516	0.123	0.477	0.433	0.455	6.25	0.444	0.472	0.458
0.041	0.571	0.538	0.555	0.041	0.5	0.446	0.473	3.125	0.506	0.491	0.499
0.014	0.577	0.538	0.558	0.014	0.51	0.482	0.496	1.5625	0.505	0.502	0.504
0.005	0.563	0.575	0.569	0.005	0.584	0.546	0.565	0.78125	0.547	0.507	0.527

Legend: DMSO – Dimethyl Sulphoxide

Table 1 shows the absorbance readings for the first trial of the experiment. In the assay, three solutions were used as treatment for the A549 cancer cells. In general, higher absorbance reading translates to more viable cells attained after the addition of solution. Inversely, lower absorbance reading is interpreted as less live cells remaining after treatment, which suggests cytotoxic activity of the solution added (Riss *et al.*, 2016). For the concentrations used, the negative control DMSO and positive control Doxorubicin were diluted three-fold from 10 µg/mL to 0.005 µg/mL. The *E. pulcherrima* extract was diluted two-fold from 100 µg/mL to 0.78125 µg/mL. All three solutions were measured spectrophotometrically at 570 nanometers and were read twice. DMSO is used as the negative control because its purpose is to dissolve formazan crystals formed after incubation with the MTT dye. It has no direct effect on the viability of the cancer cells (Riss *et al.*, 2016). Results for DMSO are considered as baseline to determine any cytotoxic activity from the *E. pulcherrima* extract. As shown in Table 1, absorbance readings for DMSO are relatively higher, from the highest concentration used (10 µg/mL) down to the lowest concentration

(0.005 µg/mL), compared to the positive control doxorubicin. The averaged absorbance readings are highest in 0.005 µg/mL concentration at 0.569, and lowest in 10 µg/mL at 0.491. An increasing trend in absorbance readings can also be observed for DMSO as the concentration decreases. These results will be compared against the positive control doxorubicin and *E. pulcherrima* extract to evaluate cytotoxicity against A549 cell line.

The effect of the positive control doxorubicin against A549 cells are also manifested in the table. Doxorubicin is a widely used chemotherapeutic drug for the treatment of different types of cancer, including leukemia, lymphoma, and cancer of the breast, liver, and kidney, among others (Weiss, 1992). It belongs to a type of chemotherapeutic drugs called anthracycline, which slows or stops the growth of cancer cells by blocking an enzyme called topoisomerase-2. This enzyme is needed by the cancer cells to divide and grow (Weiss, 1992). As shown in Table 1, absorbance readings of cancer cells treated with doxorubicin are relatively lower compared to absorbance readings treated with DMSO. Averaged results are highest in 0.005 µg/mL concentration at 0.565, and lowest in 3.333 µg/mL at 0.172. This means that more cancer cells were destroyed at 3.333 µg/mL of doxorubicin, and lesser cells were inhibited at 0.005 µg/mL, however cytotoxicity is still evident in all concentrations (Yeung, *et al.*, 2004). An increasing trend in absorbance readings can also be observed as the concentration decreases. Lower absorbance readings in comparison to DMSO means that

the cancer cells were destroyed by doxorubicin (Yeung, *et al.*, 2004).

For the *E. pulcherrima* extract, averaged absorbance readings are also noticeably lower compared to the negative control DMSO. Results were lowest in 50 µg/mL at 0.442, and highest in 0.78125 at 0.527. This means that more cancer cells were inhibited at 50 µg/mL, and lesser cells were inhibited at 0.78125, still with all concentrations exhibiting cytotoxicity because of the decrease in absorbance readings in comparison with the negative control DMSO (Yeung, *et al.*, 2004). Consistent with the negative control and positive control, an increasing trend in the absorbance readings can also be observed as the concentration decreases. Lower absorbance readings in comparison to DMSO means that *E. pulcherrima* exhibits some cytotoxic activity (Yeung, *et al.*, 2004).

Table 2. Absorbance readings of treated A549 cells.

Trial 2											
Treatment											
DMSO			Doxorubicin			<i>Euphorbia pulcherrima</i>					
Conc. (µg/mL)	Absorbance		Conc. (µg/mL)	Absorbance		Conc. (µg/mL)	Absorbance		Ave.		
	Ave.			Ave.			Ave.		Ave.		
10.000	0.495	0.487	0.491	10.000	0.362	0.371	0.367	100	0.369	0.362	0.366
3.333	0.523	0.523	0.523	3.333	0.202	0.186	0.194	50	0.441	0.448	0.445
1.111	0.53	0.52	0.525	1.111	0.277	0.356	0.317	25	0.47	0.467	0.469
0.370	0.507	0.505	0.506	0.370	0.456	0.432	0.444	12.5	0.47	0.473	0.472
0.123	0.527	0.547	0.537	0.123	0.467	0.431	0.449	6.25	0.483	0.476	0.480
0.041	0.558	0.55	0.554	0.041	0.463	0.442	0.453	3.125	0.528	0.534	0.531
0.014	0.555	0.538	0.547	0.014	0.484	0.465	0.475	1.5625	0.535	0.538	0.537
0.005	0.591	0.574	0.583	0.005	0.575	0.564	0.570	0.78125	0.582	0.587	0.585

Legend: DMSO – Dimethyl Sulphoxide

Table 2 shows the absorbance readings for the second trial of the experiment still with the use of the three solutions. Evidently, results of the second trial is consistent with the first trial. For DMSO, averaged absorbance reading is lowest in 10

µg/mL at 0.491, and highest in 0.005 µg/mL at 0.583. For doxorubicin, averaged absorbance reading is lowest in 3.333 µg/mL at 0.194, and highest in 0.005 µg/mL at 0.570. This means that cell inhibition was more evident at 3.333 µg/mL, and less evident at 0.005 µg/mL. This translates to doxorubicin inhibiting some of the viable A549 cancer cells (Yeung, *et al.*, 2004). For the *E. pulcherrima* extract, averaged absorbance reading is lowest in 100 µg/mL at 0.366, and highest in 0.78125 µg/mL at 0.585. This shows that more cancer cells were destroyed at 100 µg/mL and least cell were destroyed at 0.78125 µg/mL, still with all concentrations showing cytotoxicity (Yeung, *et al.*, 2004). Doxorubicin and *E. pulcherrima* extract gave relatively lower absorbance readings compared to DMSO. This shows that the doxorubicin and *E. pulcherrima* extract exhibited cytotoxic activity against the A549 cancer cells (Yeung, *et al.*, 2004). An increasing trend can also be observed as the concentration decreases for the three solutions.

Table 3. Absorbance readings of treated A549 cells.

Trial 3											
Treatment											
DMSO			Doxorubicin				<i>Euphorbia pulcherrima</i>				
Conc. (µg/mL)	Absorbance		Conc. (µg/mL)	Absorbance			Conc. (µg/mL)	Absorbance			
	Ave.			Ave.				Av			
10.000	0.532	0.525	0.529	10.000	0.343	0.363	0.353	100	0.396	0.404	0.
3.333	0.58	0.575	0.578	3.333	0.265	0.194	0.230	50	0.47	0.491	0.4
1.111	0.565	0.558	0.562	1.111	0.317	0.404	0.361	25	0.523	0.523	0.5
0.370	0.593	0.546	0.570	0.370	0.508	0.419	0.464	12.5	0.529	0.533	0.5
0.123	0.592	0.573	0.583	0.123	0.466	0.426	0.446	6.25	0.538	0.556	0.5
0.041	0.633	0.636	0.635	0.041	0.488	0.46	0.474	3.125	0.597	0.607	0.6
0.014	0.613	0.599	0.606	0.014	0.521	0.499	0.51	1.5625	0.586	0.6	0.5
0.005	0.656	0.612	0.634	0.005	0.613	0.59	0.602	0.78125	0.662	0.669	0.6

Legend: DMSO – Dimethyl Sulphoxide

Table 3 shows the absorbance readings for the third trial of the experiment.

Data from Table 3 for the third trial shows consistency with results from Tables 1 and 2. For DMSO, averaged absorbance reading is lowest in 10 µg/mL at 0.529, and highest in 0.041 µg/mL at 0.635. For doxorubicin, averaged absorbance reading is lowest in 3.333 µg/mL at 0.230, and highest in 0.005 µg/mL at 0.602. This means that cell inhibition is more evident at 3.333 µg/mL, and least evident at 0.005 µg/mL (Yeung, *et al.*, 2004). These results agree with the previous trials and therefore indicates cytotoxicity from doxorubicin. For the *E. pulcherrima* extract, averaged absorbance reading is lowest in 100 µg/mL at 0.4, and highest in 0.78125 µg/mL at 0.666. This also indicates inhibitory capacity of the plant extract against the A549 cancer cells being more evident at 100 µg/mL and least evident at 0.78125 µg/mL, while all concentrations still exhibiting cytotoxicity (Yeung, *et al.*, 2004). Parallel to the first and second trials, Doxorubicin and *E. pulcherrima* extract revealed relatively lower absorbance readings compared to DMSO, as well as an increasing trend in absorbance readings as the concentration of the three solution decreases.

Comparison of the absorbance readings of doxorubicin and *E. pulcherrima* extract in three trials shows little difference. Being a chemotherapeutic drug, doxorubicin was expected to produce lower absorbance reading than the extract. However, the extract also gave lower absorbance reading than the negative control, and only has ± 0.1 difference in the absorbance reading compared to doxorubicin. This suggests some cytotoxic activity from the *E. pulcherrima* extract.

Cytotoxic Activity Measured by Percent Inhibition

Table 4. Percent Inhibition computed from the absorbance readings of each concentration of the positive control, doxorubicin, against A549 cell line.

Conc ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Doxorubicin								
	Trial 1			Trial 2			Trial 3		
	Ave.			Ave.			Ave.		
10.000	31.77	30.55	31.16	26.27	24.44	25.34	35.10	31.32	33.21
3.333	61.81	69.25	65.53	61.38	64.44	62.91	54.11	66.41	60.26
1.111	49.12	41.68	45.4	47.24	32.19	39.72	43.54	28.05	35.8
0.370	9.81	17.94	13.88	9.88	14.62	12.25	10.80	26.43	18.62
0.123	7.47	16.00	11.74	13.04	19.74	16.39	20.00	26.87	23.44
0.041	9.83	19.57	14.7	16.43	20.22	18.33	23.09	27.50	25.3
0.014	8.52	13.54	11.03	11.45	14.91	13.18	4.67	8.69	6.68
0.005	-2.64	4.04	0.7	1.29	3.18	2.24	3.31	6.94	5.13

Table 4 shows the percent inhibition of the concentrations of the positive control doxorubicin. The values were obtained by encoding the absorbance readings into the software GraphPad Prism 6. GraphPad Prism 6 employs non-linear regression curve fit on the computed percent inhibition per concentration of the sample. For the first trial, averaged percent inhibition is highest in 3.333 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at 65.53%, and lowest at 0.005 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at 0.7%. For the second trial, averaged percent inhibition is still highest at 3.333 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at 62.91%, and lowest also at 0.005 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at 2.24%. In parallel to the results of the first and second trial, the third trial shows that the averaged percent inhibition is highest at 3.333 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, and lowest at 0.005 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. (Please see Figure 3 on page 27). This means that doxorubicin is most potent in at 3.333 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in relation to its inhibitory capacity, and least potent at 0.005 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Susanti, *et al*, 2007).

Table 5. Percent Inhibition computed from the absorbance readings of each

concentration of *Euphorbia pulcherrima* against A549 cell line.

Conc ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	<i>Euphorbia pulcherrima</i>								
	Trial 1			Trial 2			Trial 3		
	Ave.			Ave.			Ave.		
100	-	29.12	-0.31	24.85	26.27	25.56	25.07	23.56	24.32
	29.74								
50	12.16	10.15	11.16	15.68	14.34	15.01	18.61	14.98	16.8
25	12.56	9.78	11.17	10.48	11.05	10.77	6.86	6.86	6.86
12.5	12.98	8.82	10.9	7.11	6.52	6.82	7.11	6.41	6.76
6.25	13.87	8.44	11.16	10.06	11.36	10.71	7.64	4.55	6.1
3.125	8.75	11.45	10.1	4.69	3.61	4.15	5.91	4.33	5.12
1.5625	9.42	9.96	9.69	2.10	1.56	1.83	3.30	0.99	2.15
0.78125	3.87	10.90	7.39	0.09	-0.77	-0.68	-4.42	-5.52	-4.97

Table 5 presents the percent inhibition of the *E. pulcherrima* extract. For the first trial, averaged percent inhibition is highest in 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at 11.17%, and lowest in 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at -0.31%. For the second trial, averaged percent inhibition is highest in 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at 25.56%, and lowest in 0.78125 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at -4.42%. For the third trial, averaged percent inhibition is highest in 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at 24.32%, and lowest in 0.78125 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at -4.97%. These results reveal the inhibitory capacity of *E. pulcherrima* extract. In reference to the table above, *E. pulcherrima* extract at 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ exhibits the highest values for cell inhibition, which means the extract is most potent against A549 cells in said concentration, and lowest percent inhibition at 0.78125 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, which means it is least potent in said concentration. (Susanti, *et al*, 2007). It is evident that with the exception of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for the first trial and 0.78125 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for the second and third trials, all other concentrations of *E. pulcherrima* extract exhibits cytotoxic effect towards A549 human lung adenocarcinoma cell line.

Statistical Analysis in the Absorbance Readings of *E. pulcherrima* Extract and Doxorubicin

Table 6. Significant Difference in the absorbance readings of the *E. pulcherrima* extract and positive control Doxorubicin.

Concentration (µg/mL)	T-test value	p-value*	Verbal Interpretation
100	1.393	0.222	Not significant
50	18.015	0.000	Significant
25	10.209	0.000	Significant
12.5	2.048	0.096	Not significant
6.25	2.011	0.101	Not significant
3.125	3.810	0.012	Significant
1.5625	3.264	0.022	Significant
0.78125	0.714	0.507	Not significant

* - at 0.05 level of significance

Table 6 shows the significant difference between the absorbance readings of doxorubicin and the *E. pulcherrima* extract. Results of the statistical analysis shows that doxorubicin and *E. pulcherrima* extract at 100 µg/mL, 12.5 µg/mL, 6.25 µg/mL, and 0.78125 µg/mL shows no significant difference, while doxorubicin and *E. pulcherrima* at 50 µg/mL, 25 µg/mL, 3.125 µg/mL, and 1.5625 µg/mL shows significant difference between the results. Concentrations with no significant difference in their absorbance readings mean that there is little deviation from the results of doxorubicin and *E. pulcherrima* extract, which correlates to their cytotoxic activity against cancer cells (Ulbrich, K., Etrych, T., Chytil, P., Jelínková, M., & Říhová, B., 2003). This is important for the *E. pulcherrima* extract because being compared to and having no significant difference to the results of doxorubicin, which is an anti-tumor drug, means that the plant extract also exhibits cytotoxic property. In reference to the table above, cell inhibition is most potent in *E. pulcherrima* at concentrations of 100 µg/mL, 12.5 µg/mL, 6.25 µg/mL, and 0.78125 µg/mL, which means *E. pulcherrima*

extract in said concentrations is most effective in destroying cancer cells.

Statistical Analysis in the Absorbance Readings of *E. pulcherrima* Extract and DMSO

Table 7. Significant Difference in the absorbance readings of *E. pulcherrima* extract and negative control dimethyl sulphoxide.

Concentration (µg/mL)	T-test value	p-value*	Verbal interpretation
100	2.086	0.091	Not significant
50	8.510	0.000	Significant
25	9.325	0.000	Significant
12.5	4.596	0.006	Significant
6.25	5.369	0.003	Significant
3.125	5.367	0.003	Significant
1.5625	2.325	0.068	Not significant
0.78125	0.170	0.872	Not significant

* - at 0.05 level of significance

Table 7 shows the significant difference between the absorbance readings of *E. pulcherrima* extract and the negative control DMSO. Results of the statistical analysis shows that the plant extract at 100 µg/mL, 1.5625 µg/mL, and 0.78125 µg/mL shows no significant difference, while the plant extract at 50 µg/mL, 25 µg/mL, 12.5 µg/mL, 6.25 µg/mL, and 3.125 µg/mL shows significant difference between the results. DMSO, being the negative control, is expected not have inhibitory capacity against the A549 cell line. In correlation with *E. pulcherrima* extract, having significant difference against the absorbance readings of DMSO will correlate to its inhibitory capacity (Ulbrich, K., Etrych, T., Chytil, P., Jelínková, M., & Říhová, B., 2003). In reference to the table above, cell inhibition is more evident in *E. pulcherrima* concentrations of 50 µg/mL, 25 µg/mL, 12.5 µg/mL, 6.25 µg/mL, and 3.125 µg/mL, which

means *E. pulcherrima* extract in said concentrations is most effective in cell inhibition.

Conclusion

Based on the results gathered through evaluation of cytotoxic property of *E. pulcherrima* extract against A549 human lung adenocarcinoma cell line, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Absorbance readings of *E. pulcherrima* extract was lower than that of the negative control DMSO. The researchers therefore conclude that there is some cytotoxic activity exhibited by the plant extract towards the A549 human lung adenocarcinoma cell line.
2. Percent inhibition is evident in almost all concentrations of *E. pulcherrima* extract except at 100 µg/mL for the first trial and 0.78125 µg/mL for the second and third trial, and is highest at 100 µg/mL in average. This means that the *E. pulcherrima* extract has inhibitory capacity against the A549 cancer cell line and is most potent at 100 µg/mL.
3. There is no significant difference between the absorbance readings of the *E. pulcherrima* extract and the positive control doxorubicin, specifically at concentrations of 100 µg/mL, 12.5 µg/mL, 6.25 µg/mL, and 0.78125 µg/mL. This further supports the findings of the researchers that the plant extract exhibits cytotoxic activity towards the cancer cells.
4. There is a significant difference between the absorbance readings of

- 5.
6. the *E. pulcherrima* extract and the negative control dimethyl sulphoxide, specifically at concentrations of 50 µg/mL, 25 µg/mL, 12.5 µg/mL, 6.25 µg/mL, and 3.125 µg/mL. This validates the findings that *E. pulcherrima* extract inhibits A549 cancer cells and therefore manifests cytotoxic property.

Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusions presented the following recommendations are forwarded:

- Further studies may be conducted using another protocol (CAM assay, ATP assay, etc.) that can measure the cytotoxic activity of the plant extract.
- Further studies may be conducted using other solvent for extraction which may affect biochemical compounds of the plant, reducing its cytotoxic potential.
- Further studies may employ methods of extraction other than using Soxhlet apparatus.
- A comparative study may be conducted using multiple cell lines to evaluate which cell line would the plant extract exhibit more cytotoxic activity.
- A study may be conducted to determine if there is a difference in the cytotoxic potential between the green and red foliage of *Euphorbia pulcherrima*.

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